

Fully dynamic carbon footprint of circular biobased systems – A framework with temporal life cycle inventory database (DyPLCA) tailored for forestry and wood products cascades

Thomas Schaubroeck¹, Tomas Navarrete-Gutiérrez¹, Thomas Gibon¹, Alya Bolowich¹, Laurent Chion¹, Tianran Ding¹, Ligia Tiruta-Barna², Massimo Pizzol³, Kira Lancz³, Ricardo Méndez⁴, Eduardo Entrena-Barbero⁴, Josefin Neuwirth⁵, Tomas Rydberg⁵, Ellen Riise⁶, Pernilla Cederstrand⁶, Tamara Coello-Garcia⁷, Dieuwertje Schrijvers⁸, Alexander Charpentier Poncelet⁸ and Enrico Benetto¹

¹ Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg

² TBI, Université de Toulouse, CNRS, INRAE, INSA, Toulouse, France

³ Department of Sustainability and Planning, Aalborg University, Aalborg, Denmark

⁴ Contactica, Madrid, Spain

⁵ IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute, Stockholm, Sweden

⁶ ESSITY, Stockholm, Sweden

⁷ CESEFOR, Soria, Spain

⁸ WeLOOP, Lambersart, France

E-mail contact: thomas.schaubroeck@list.lu

1. Introduction

Global concerns about climate change and its impacts induced by greenhouse gas emissions and processes make it crucial to understand its evolution over time. This is particularly relevant for biobased systems, which take up CO₂ during biomass growth, of which a part remains stored during the life cycle of products (considering possible recycling, reuse etc.), and there is an eventual release at the final end of life (e.g. via incineration). However, in the field of life cycle assessment (LCA) and carbon footprint analysis, which focuses on the evaluation of product systems, a static view is still the dominant approach. Few studies have considered dynamic effects, and if so, only by taking into account time differentiation for the foreground system [1]. Therefore, it is only recently that a fully dynamic LCA has been applied (in this case, dynamic only implies temporal differentiation), in particular through the dynamic process-based LCA (DyPLCA) framework, tool and related temporal database [2]. Yet, there are several aspects needing improvement, four of which were selected for the focus of this study: ranging from providing an updated respective background temporal database and impact assessment methods to improving the modeling of carbon fluxes for circular biobased systems, in this case forestry and wood products cascading. A framework has been developed to tackle these gaps, as specified in the next section. An application to two cases of the CALIMERO project is envisioned: (1) one on laminated strand lumber (LSL) & (2) the Swedish pulp and paper sector.

2. Materials and Methods

In this section we present the overall methodological framework for an improved fully dynamic LCA of circular biobased systems, and its four advancements to address respective identified gaps.

First, the DyPLCA temporal database is a collection of temporal data for all ecoinvent 3.2 processes [2]. Currently, ecoinvent 3.9 is available and contains updated information and new processes. Hence, a straightforward improvement we have done for this framework is the update of the DyPLCA database by LIST in the CALIMERO and LCA4BIO projects.

Second, in the respective DyPLCA database, the temporal flows of forestry systems, especially greenhouse gases, have been considered in a simplistic manner [2]. Emission amounts and their temporal distributions are improved based on the outcomes of a flexible parametric model for a balanced account of forest carbon fluxes in LCA [3]. The latter model projects the CO₂ flows for different management practices and tree species. This tool is developed by Aalborg University and is improved, in particular in the context of the ALIGNED project, and used in our framework.

A *third gap* relates to the need to update the climate change impact assessment. INSA Toulouse has developed an advanced tool that already covers different types of effects over time and is compatible with DyPLCA outcomes [4]. This tool and its dataset will be updated based on the latest information and data from the IPCC and other alike-sources, to lead to a better characterization of climate change impact.

The final and fourth gap of concern is the limited tailored loop modelling for wood cascading systems in ecoinvent and DyPLCA. This is ameliorated by (a) easily including usage processes that cover the duration of in-use lifetime, (b) incorporating aspects and parameters that represent and allow easy modification of the number of loops, and (c) considering improved accounting or modelling of recycling/reuse effects (related to the issue of multifunctionality of waste valorization), building on previous work [4]. The latter will also apply a distinction between attributional, consequential and standard (e.g. ISO 14067) perspectives.

Figure 1: Description of the proposed methodological framework, with four advancements specified.

3. Results and Discussion

Several developments of the framework are ongoing. The most elaborate is the update of the DyPLCA database, which has already been going through the first step. The initial screening shows that several thousand new processes are available in ecoinvent 3.9 compared to ecoinvent 3.2, which means that further systematic steps are needed. Results on the two case studies are being finalized as well.

4. Conclusions

This framework will allow to have a highly improved fully dynamic carbon footprint of circular biobased systems, with a focus on the forest-based ones. We aim to finalize all foreseen developments, but the orientation and intermediate results will be informative, given the ambition of the overall research.

5. Bibliography

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